

UTILIZING MODERN TEACHING METHODS FOR LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

Umirzokov Sharofiddin

JSPU, Jizzakh, Uzbekistan.

ANNOTATION: Children to strengthen their interest in being different from the first study on the subject's imagination, diligence, perseverance, lucidity, as an aspect of activity to overestimate the role and importance of preschool education institutions.

KEY WORDS: Strengthen, subject's imagination, diligence, perseverance, lucidity, preschool education, technologies, preparatory schools, elementary schools, tier system.

Under President Islam Karimov's leadership, there has been a significant focus on education reform in the Republic of Uzbekistan, particularly in the area of primary and preschool education. The Ministry of Education has reported an increase in the number of state-owned schools and non-governmental educational institutions, including kindergartens, catering to over 581.6 thousand children.

Currently, secondary schools in the Republic are equipped with modern computer labs that feature electronic textbooks and manuals. The integration of computer technology is not limited to scientific subjects only but extends to the teaching of foreign languages as well. Utilizing electronic resources such as textbooks, multimedia content, and audio aids is deemed essential for effective language instruction.

The incorporation of educational technologies into the learning process is emphasized, facilitating training and professional development opportunities for individuals to enhance their skills through the use of information and communication technologies. By leveraging these tools, teachers and school administrators can improve management systems and create more engaging educational materials. Moreover, the study of foreign languages is influenced by various factors, including the country's political, economic, and cultural landscape, international relations, and global language trends. The availability of resources and prioritization of languages, such as English in today's context, play a crucial role in shaping language learning objectives.

The current focus is on promoting the acquisition of at least two modern foreign languages, with an increased emphasis on prioritizing the learning of foreign languages as the initial language of study. This emphasis is particularly significant in the early stages of education, such as preparatory schools, kindergartens, or primary schools, where the first foreign language serves as a stepping stone to mastering additional languages.

While many parents view English as an essential language for future global communication and career prospects, it is essential to recognize that there are numerous other languages with wide regional variations and community-specific applications. Introducing languages other than English as the primary foreign language can help broaden children's perspectives and sustain their interest in language learning beyond English.

Contrary to concerns about complicating the language learning process, exposing children to a variety of foreign languages can foster a comparative and immersive language learning experience. By instilling a positive attitude towards foreign language learning from an early age, children can gradually incorporate and

build upon their language skills, ultimately enhancing their proficiency in languages like English over time.

It is crucial to offer children the flexibility to choose the foreign languages they wish to learn, as this approach enables them to engage more readily and master the language effectively. Encouraging children to explore new and unfamiliar languages can spark their curiosity and facilitate communication in diverse cultural contexts, ultimately fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation for different languages and cultures.

In the early stages of language learning, children typically grasp word meanings and phrases in their native language as a foundation for understanding foreign languages. Despite initial challenges in comprehending grammatical structures, children tend to assimilate foreign language components through familiar phrases and expressions as they progress in their language acquisition journey.

Education strategies for teaching foreign languages should align with the developmental needs and interests of individual children. Emphasizing emotional engagement and creating a supportive learning environment where children feel safe to explore and inquire can enhance their participation and enthusiasm for language learning. By tailoring language education to accommodate children's unique learning styles and fostering positive relationships with educators, children can actively engage in the language learning process and deepen their linguistic skills effectively.

The focus is on incorporating interesting topics delivered through games to enhance experimentation and creativity, leading to concise learning experiences that cater to all facets of a child's development in foreign language education for adults. It is essential for elementary classes to foster comprehensive personality development, enabling children to communicate emotionally, creatively, cognitively, and mentally

in a foreign language. Individualized assistance based on each child's developmental level is crucial for successful implementation.

A key aspect of the learning process involves creating opportunities for children to ask questions, share opinions, and receive corrections in a nurturing and thoughtful manner. Building a supportive language learning environment opens avenues for interaction with various individuals, such as parents, siblings, and peers, who serve as important role models. Access to written materials, independent reading and workspaces, like reading corners in preparatory and elementary schools, facilitates language skill development.

Methodological principles underscore the importance of making foreign language learning interactive and enjoyable. Emphasizing experiential learning, illustrating rules through examples, and encouraging multi-sensory engagement enable optimal comprehension and retention. Utilizing visual aids, incremental tasks, and differentiated instruction enhances understanding and application of language concepts.

Diversifying teaching strategies, such as individual, partner, small group, and whole group activities, and incorporating varied instructional methods like stations, scenarios, and projects, fosters student engagement and critical thinking. Adapting methodological approaches based on lesson content and objectives, and integrating student experiences and multilingualism in teaching contributes to effective language instruction.

In early language learning stages, children are encouraged to imitate and gradually assimilate foreign language elements by listening, understanding, and responding over time. It is beneficial for instructors to predominantly use the foreign language during lessons while occasionally resorting to the native language for effective communication. Acknowledging students' language learning experiences and leveraging their multilingual abilities enriches the teaching process, fostering a

positive learning environment that encourages students to express their opinions freely.

Primary school students are provided with educational materials encompassing information and communication technologies, software tools, multimedia, music, games, and electronic books to facilitate their development comfortably. These resources offer students the opportunity to independently engage with multimedia electronic books in educational settings and from home, enhancing their learning experiences. By utilizing these technologies, English language lessons can be conducted interactively, introducing new themes and expediting knowledge acquisition. The integration of technology in education enables real-time monitoring of student progress and offers opportunities for revising and reinforcing concepts and grammar rules.

Learning a foreign language for the first time can be challenging, particularly for elementary school students who are introduced to English language classes divided into two proficiency groups. Proficiency in one's native language is crucial for acquiring foreign languages effectively, as insufficient linguistic skills may pose obstacles to language learning. Pronunciation is also emphasized in English language instruction to ensure accurate verbal communication. Modern teaching methods, such as language rooms equipped with audiovisual aids, special presentations, and electronic games, are employed to enhance students' English language skills.

Given the complexity of teaching English in primary school, new teaching materials are regularly developed to streamline language learning without overwhelming students. Visual aids, such as drawings and poster exhibitions, are incorporated to facilitate comprehension and engagement among students. Emphasizing interactive learning over rote memorization, primary school language

courses prioritize practical application and active participation to enhance language proficiency effectively.

Educational standards for primary school language classes emphasize the importance of individualized instruction and continuous assessment to monitor students' progress systematically. Curricula for language classes are developed in alignment with learning objectives and teaching methods tailored to suit early language learners. Assessments based on thematic evaluations and point systems encourage self-assessment and improvement, fostering a culture of continuous learning and development among students.

Fostering a holistic approach to language learning that nurtures students' curiosity and maintains their interest in language skills is fundamental to achieving optimal results in small-scale adult language classes. Establishing a balance between self-assessment, external evaluation, and long-term planning is essential to sustain the efficacy of language education programs and ensure students' ongoing progress in language proficiency.

The primary focus is on utilizing technology, multimedia resources, and educational materials to enhance learning experiences for elementary school students. This encompasses tools like information and communication technologies, software, music, games, and electronic books. By accessing multimedia electronic books, students can independently acquire knowledge not only in educational settings but also remotely from home. Incorporating these resources in English language lessons facilitates interactive learning, promotes the exploration of new themes, and supports the efficient acquisition of knowledge and skills.

Integration of technology in education allows for real-time tracking of students' progress, offering opportunities to revisit and reinforce concepts and grammar rules. While learning a foreign language for the first time can be challenging, elementary school students are divided into proficient groups for

mastering English easily and conveniently. However, issues such as pronunciation and accent may arise during the initial stages of English language instruction. To address this, modern teaching methods employing auditory aids, language rooms, special presentations, and electronic games are deployed to enhance English language skills effectively.

Given the complexities of teaching English to new students and educators, the development of new textbooks tailored to overcome initial challenges is crucial. Visual aids, such as drawings and poster exhibitions, are utilized to assist children in comprehending foreign language concepts. Emphasizing practical application over theoretical rules, elementary school language courses prioritize efficient language learning methods that engage students effectively.

Educational standards for primary school language classes focus on individualized instruction and continuous assessment to ensure effective learning outcomes. The curriculum for language classes must align with educational objectives and methodologies suitable for early language learners. Assessments based on thematic evaluations and points systems encourage self-assessment and improvement, fostering a culture of ongoing learning and development among students.

Facilitating holistic language learning experiences that stimulate students' curiosity and maintain their interest in language development is key to achieving superior outcomes in small adult language classes. Balancing self-assessment, external evaluation, and long-term planning is essential for sustaining the effectiveness of language education programs, promoting continuous growth in language proficiency among students.

Furthermore, within primary education, it is essential to consider the children's age when teaching them English language fundamentals to ensure they grasp the required information effectively. Therefore, it is imperative to create an

engaging and informative learning environment for children in English. Additionally, a team of seasoned educators specializing in content, psychology, education, and information technology, as well as experts conducting research in the field, should be engaged. By employing a systematic approach to integrating information and communication technologies into English language instruction, academic literature underscores the enhancement of foreign language learning and usage within the educational framework. This systematic approach aims to bolster the efficacy of primary education in imparting foreign language skills to students.

References

1. Образование основа будущего. 2013-2017. План развития сектора образования Узбекистана.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси кадрлар тайёрлаш миллий дастури. – Т., 1997 й.
3. Сластенина В. А. Педагогическое образование: вызовы XXI века. – 2010.
4. Смолянинова О.Г. Информационные технологии и методика case-study в профессиональном обучении студентов педагогического вуза: Труды II Всероссийской научно-методической конференции "Образование XXI века: инновационные технологии диагностика и управление в целях информатизации и гуманизации"- Красноярск, май 2000.

<http://writing.colostate.edu/references/research/casestudy/index.cfm>

<http://www.ed.asu.edu/edrev/reviews/rev24.htm>

<http://www.casemethod.ru/base1>.